

**SYNONYMIC CHARACTER OF NON-IDIOMATIC PHRASEOLOGISMS
(ON THE BASIS OF ENGLISH, FRENCH AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES)**

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Phraseology of each language reflects somehow its specifics: specifics of its grammatical structure, vocabulary and the specifics of the historical way of people – its native speakers. However, besides national specifics there are some common features in phraseology, one of which is demonstrated in phraseological synonymy.

Phraseologisms can be divided into two groups, non-idiomatic and idiomatic. Let us consider non-idiomatic phraseological units (PhU). This group includes all the verbal phraseologisms “verb+noun”, where noun is used in its nominative meaning and is a semantic core of a phraseologism, and the verb possesses phraseologically related meaning, which can be either figurative:

Eng. shoot a look

Rus. втереться в доверие

Fr. coller son regard sur qqn;

either non-figurative:

Eng. to give a look

Rus. дать ответ

Fr. donner la reponse.

The meaning of a verbal phraseologism is motivated and is a sum of meanings of its semantically divided components: nominative meaning and phraseologically related meaning of a verbal component.

Synonymy of non-idiomatic phraseologisms is formed at the expense of semantic rapprochement of appropriate lexical components and each of them, due to their semantic divisibility, possesses the special role in synonymy of phraseologisms of this type.

As the nominative component appears as a bearer of a stalker meaning of non-idiomatic phraseologism, so synonymy of such phraseologisms is specified by common meaning and can be expressed either in synonymy of nouns or in nominative components of phraseologisms that are produced by the same nouns.

Presented in non-idiomatic phraseologisms in direct meaning, synonymic nouns keep their own differences and bring them into synonymy of appropriate phraseologisms. Let us consider some examples:

English synonyms *need* and *want* are differentiated by their translation, as the first one means ‘to require something vitally important’, and the second one means ‘to require something desirable, necessary for convenience, etc.’ The same differences belong to the synonyms:

to be in need of – to be in want of.

In the Russian language, the word *ярость* differs from its synonym *бешенство* by the level of fury when the subject loses his temper and sanity. The very difference characterizes synonyms-phraseologisms:

прийти в ярость – прийти в бешенство.

In the French language, the term *main* (part of the arm from elbow until fingers) differs from the term *bras* (part of the arm from shoulder until elbow). This divergence in the meaning is also reflected in phraseological units (PhU), which contain these words:

donner la main – donner le bras.

Semantic relations between verbal components of non-idiomatic phraseologisms are more figurative.

The existence of a large quantity of semantic relations between verbal components more than between nominative components is explained by the fact that by making non-idiomatic phraseologisms, the verbs are reconsidered, i.e. they obtain phraseologically related meanings which are divided into nuances, connected with the certain phraseological units.

Non-idiomatic phraseologisms also possess stylistic synonymy, which appears at the expense of the following:

1. nominative components introduce their stylistic peculiarities in nominative meaning:

Eng. give permission – give leave

Russ. потупить взор – потупить взгляд

Fr. accorder la permission – accorder l'autorisation.

2. The verbs – stylistic synonyms in nominative meaning do not lose their stylistic characteristics during formation phraseologically related meanings and introduce their synonymy of the appropriate phraseologisms:

Eng. give permission – grant permission

Russ. сделать ошибку – совершить ошибку

Fr. Faire une erreur – commettre une erreur.

3. Some verbs, which do not possess stylistic phone in nominative meaning, can obtain it during the formation of certain phraseologically related meanings. For example, the verbs *render/give*, *render/faire*, *попасть/влипнуть* in phraseologisms:

Eng. render assistance

Russ. попасть в историю

Fr. Rendre une visite.

Let us compare them with the synonyms:

Eng. give assistance

Russ. влипнуть в историю

Fr. faire une visite.

Synonymy of non-idiomatic verbal phraseologisms consists of the following types of synonyms: ideographic, stylistic-ideographic and stylistic, which are the least in quantity in this group.

REFERENCES

1. Amriddinova, N. (2022). The role of context in realization of semantic structure of the text. Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities, 13, 60-63.
2. Amriddinova, N. S. (2020). Some Aspects of Correlation in Semantic Actualization of Phraseological Units. Modern Views and Research, 183.
3. Hornby A.S. Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary of Current English. Oxford:1998

4. Кунин А.В. Фразеология современного английского языка. – М.: 1993
5. Рецкера Я.И. Французско-русский фразеологический словарь. М.: 2003